

Strength Distribution of Ceramic Fibers Including Defects on Interfacial Reaction Layer

Koichi Goda and Hideharu Fukunaga
Faculty of Engineering,
Hiroshima University,
Saijo, Higashi-Hiroshima, 724,
JAPAN

ABSTRACT

An approach was developed to the strength distribution of ceramic fibers including a reaction layer at the interface between the fiber and the matrix metal. A Weibull distribution was applied to the strength distributions caused by internal defects in the fiber, and also to the strength distribution by cracks formed by the premature fracture of the reaction layer. The total distribution of the fiber strength was given by a competing-risk model among the Weibull distributions. Then, the scale parameter estimated by the cause of the reaction layer's crack, was assumed to be given by monotonic decreasing function of reacting time. The average value and the coefficient of variation predicted from the model were in good agreement with the tensile-test data of SiC fibers. It was pointed out, moreover, that the reaction layer's crack was a dangerous defect for a fiber, provided that the orientation of each inner defect in the fiber was at random.

INTRODUCTION

There are many reports on the strength degradation of ceramic fibers due to reacting with matrix metal [1]-[3]. The fracture mechanism of the fibers has been described from the stress concentration effect of a crack originated from the premature fracture of the brittle reaction layer. Ochiai et al. reported [3][4] that the degraded fiber strength was theoretically given as a function of the thickness of the reaction layer. However, their achievement was a deterministic evaluation of strength by fracture mechanics. We previously reported [5] on aluminum-coated SiC fibers that the scatter of the strength was changed with the annealing time, while the strength itself was changed. In many of reports [6]-[8] which deals with the

theoretical and simulative treatment of a FRM fracture, the fiber strength is generally evaluated as a random variable. Here is enough necessity to describe the probabilistic strength of the fiber having the reaction layer's crack.

The present paper gives the strength distribution function of ceramic fibers including the reaction layer' cracks. We consider that the strength distribution is determined by a competing-risk model [9] among the strength distributions of the defect's populations inherent in the fiber and the strength distribution of such cracks on the fiber surface. And a multi-modal Weibull distribution [10] was employed for it. It was proved that the analytical average values and the coefficient of variation obtained from the distribution function were in good agreement with the experimental data of SiC fibers. Additionally, it has been discussed about the reason why a lower fiber strength was induced by the reaction layer's crack, on the condition that the directions of the inner defects in the fiber were randomly oriented and under equitriaxial tension a Weibull distribution was realized.

ANALYTICAL PROCEDURE

Probabilistic treatment of strength by reaction layer's crack

Figure 1 shows the fracture surface of a coreless SiC fiber (produced by Nippon Carbon Co., Ltd., Trade name: Nicalon) by SEM. This fiber was annealed at a temperature of 700°C for 0.5min, after aluminum coating. As indicated by a white arrow, the initial point of the fracture may be a product caused by the reaction between the fiber and the coated aluminum. This reaction layer is weaker than the internal defects pre-existing in the fiber, so that the fiber's fracture would be due to the notch effect caused by this layer's fracture. It is observed from the figure that the reaction products exist spottedly on the fiber surface here and there. Therefore, it is considered that the fiber was connected with the aluminum by many of the point joints, and the reaction may be extended around the point by an annealing treatment.

Assuming that a crack equivalent to the reaction layer's thickness c occurs along the direction normal to the loading one, as indicated by Ochiai et al. [4] and Shorshorov et al. [11], the infinitely-remote tensile stress σ acting on the fiber is shown as follows [11];

$$\sigma = Y\kappa \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{\pi c}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Fractograph of SiC fiber initiated at the reaction layer.

where, Y is a constant depending on the crack shape, κ is a constant determined by the elasticity of the reaction layer and the fiber, K_I is the stress intensity factor of Mode I. In this case the crack extension criteria is $K_I = K_{Ic}$. K_{Ic} is a fracture toughness of the fiber. Each thickness of the reaction layer may be scattered depending on a temperature distribution in the annealing furnace and a non-homogeneity of the fiber surface's composition and so on. That

is to say, it can be a value subjected to a probabilistic function. For example, it has been reported [12] that in C/Ni composites the thickness was approximated to the normal distribution. Therefore, supposing that (1) each crack shape is given as the similar one to any cracks, (2) The probabilistic variation of the fracture toughness of each fiber is negligible, the fracture strength of the fiber is determined dependent on the maximum thickness c_{max} of the reaction layer as follows;

$$\sigma_f = Y\kappa \frac{K_{Ic}}{\sqrt{\pi c_{max}}} \quad (2)$$

The c_{max} is also considered to be a random variable distributed by each fiber. The distribution of c_{max} is statistically equal to that of the maximum value for the distribution of c . Therefore, the distribution function $F_R(\sigma)$ of the fiber strength σ caused by the reaction layer's crack is given by a Weibull distribution as follows (for simplicity, the analysis is confined to two-parameters).

$$F_R(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{OR}}\right)^{m_R}\right\} \quad (3)$$

where, m_R is a shape parameter, σ_{OR} is a scale parameter, L is a gauge length and L_0 is a standard gauge length at which Weibull parameters are estimated. Of course, in this case, it is assumed that there is no interactions among the reaction layer's cracks.

In general, the thickness of the reaction layer is increased with the increase of annealing time t and temperature T . Then, the thickness can be expressed as follows[3];

$$c = k \cdot t^n \quad (4)$$

where, n is a constant, and k is the reaction rate constant expressed by an Arrhenius type of equation containing a parameter of temperature T . Although the average thickness may be subjected to eq.(4), it is unknown whether c_{\max} is applicable to the same equation or not. The c_{\max} is closely related to the fracture strength as seen in eq.(2), so it is considered that there is some relation between Weibull parameters representing the fracture strength and the annealing time and temperature. In the present work, this is estimated by giving some reasonable assumption.

Distribution of fiber strength

If a crack in the reaction layer is very small, the fiber would be fractured by an internal defect inherent in the fiber itself. In general, ceramic fibers have several kinds of fracture modes and each of the strength is completely changed dependent on the type of the defect causing the failure [13]- [15]. For such a case, we have already reported [15] that a multi-modal Weibull distribution based on a competing-risk model gives a more reasonable result to the experimental data than that obtained from a single Weibull distribution which is usually applied. Then, the multi-modal Weibull distribution $F_I(\sigma)$ is given as follows.

$$F_I(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\frac{L}{L_0} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0i}}\right)^{m_i}\right\} \quad (5)$$

where, m_i and σ_{0i} are Weibull parameters in a strength distribution of a defect's population i ($i=1, \dots, k$). If the reaction layer's cracks and the internal defects have no interaction each other, the strength distribution of the fiber is given from the standpoint of the competing-risk model [9] as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} F(\sigma) &= 1 - \{1 - F_I(\sigma)\}\{1 - F_R(\sigma)\} \\ &= 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{L}{L_0} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0i}}\right)^{m_i} + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0R}}\right)^{m_R} \right\}\right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Eq.(6) is also a form of the multi-modal Weibull distribution. The equation giving the average strength μ of eq.(6) is as follows;

$$\mu = \int_0^{\infty} \sigma \frac{\partial F(\sigma)}{\partial \sigma} d\sigma \quad (7)$$

This equation cannot be obtained as an analytical form, so μ has been found by the numerical integration. The coefficient of variation c.o.v. is given by the following equation;

$$\text{c.o.v.} = \left\{ \int_0^{\infty} (\sigma - \mu)^2 \frac{\partial F(\sigma)}{\partial \sigma} d\sigma \right\}^{1/2} / \mu \quad (8)$$

Estimation of Weibull parameters

For estimating Weibull parameters, a maximum likelihood estimation method was employed. The multi-modal Weibull distribution is based on the competing-risk model and hence the likelihood function of eq.(6) is given by

$$L = C \left(\prod_{i=1}^k L_i \right) L_R \quad (9)$$

where,

$$L_i = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^{n_i} f_i(\sigma_j^i) \right\} \left[\prod_{i=1}^k \prod_{j=1}^{n_i} \{1 - F_i(\sigma_j^i)\} \right] \prod_{j=1}^{n_R} \{1 - F_i(\sigma_j^R)\}$$

and,

$$L_R = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^{n_R} f_R(\sigma_j^R) \right\} \left[\prod_{i=1}^k \prod_{j=1}^{n_i} \{1 - F_R(\sigma_j^i)\} \right]$$

C is a constant $(= n! / (\prod_{i=1}^k n_i! n_R!))$, n_i is a number of samples fractured by the cause of defect "i" at stress $\sigma_1^i, \dots, \sigma_{n_i}^i (i=1, \dots, k)$. n_R is a number of samples fractured from the reaction layer at stress $\sigma_1^R, \dots, \sigma_{n_R}^R$. Since L_1, \dots, L_k and L_R contain only Weibull parameters described by defects "1", ..., "k" and "R", respectively, the method of finding out maximum likelihood estimators on each likelihood can be applied [10]. Each likelihood equation used is as follows;

$$\frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \ln \sigma_j^i - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \sigma_j^{m_i} \cdot \ln \sigma_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \sigma_j^{m_i}} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{0i} = \left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \sigma_j^{m_i} \right)^{1/m_i}$$

In the estimation of L_R , each suffix "i" in eq.(10) should be exchanged to "R". In the present work, the first equation of eq.(10) has been solved by the Newton-Raphson method.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Weibull Plots of SiC Fibers and the Estimation of Weibull Parameters

Figure 2 shows Weibull plots ranging by a mean rank method against the tensile strength of SiC fibers reported in the reference [5]. The fibers were coated with aluminum by vapour deposition in a vacuum of about 1.33×10^{-3} Pa, and were annealed at 700°C for 0.5, 1, 2 and 5min, respectively. The results

of the tensile test and the SEM observation showed that the fibers had three kinds of the fracture modes, i.e. initiated at a flaw or a pit type of surface defect "1", a void type of inner defect "2" and a reaction layer type of defect "R". The cause of the fracture has been investigated one by one. It is seen from the figure that the fibers fractured at the reaction layer are increased in number with the annealing time, and in the conditions beyond 1min, all the fibers are finally failed at the layer. Moreover, the slope of the plots is gradually enlarged. That means a decrease of the coefficient of variation.

Figure 2. Weibull plots of SiC fibers.

The estimates of Weibull parameters for each annealing time are shown in Table 1. It is seen that m_1 , m_2 and m_R are in the range of about 3.8-4.7, 5.4-9.5 and 6.2-8.0, respectively. It is well known that the shape parameter is largely scattered in a small sample number. The present results may have the same tendency. On the other hand, the scale parameter σ_{01} and σ_{02} are in the range of about 3.6-4.6 and 4.2-5.2, respectively. However, σ_{0R} is conspicuously decreased with the annealing time.

Prediction of the Average Strength of Fibers and the Coefficient of Variation

Table 1 shows that each m_R is almost a constant value, but σ_{0R} is

TABLE 1. Weibull parameters of SiC fibers.

Time min	m_1	m_2	m_R	σ_{01}	σ_{02}	σ_{0R}
0	3.84	8.06	-	4.53	5.14	-
0.5	4.35	5.40	6.27	3.71	5.06	4.88
1	4.68	9.44	7.95	3.60	4.19	3.93
2	-	-	7.13	-	-	1.99
5	-	-	7.59	-	-	1.60

significantly changed with the annealing time. In the present work, it is assumed that m_R is a constant and σ_{OR} is a monotonic decreasing function of time t , in the light of eqs. (2) and (4) as follows;

$$\sigma_{OR} = k't^{-n'} \quad (11)$$

where, k' and n' are constants. In general, a Weibull's shape parameter is known to be a constant and the scale parameter is changed dependent on the volume or the surface area of the material.

So, this assumption is reasonable to some extent, although the physical meaning is not still clear. On starting the calculation, a value 7.23 was used as the average one of each shape parameter m_R , and k' (=3.45) and n' (=0.52) were obtained from the least square method. And the parameters of virgin fibers (= 0min annealing) were applied to m_1 , m_2 , σ_{01} and σ_{02} . Figure 3 shows the transition curves of the average strength and the coefficient of variation predicted from eqs.(7) and (8) with the annealing time. It is proved that the curves are in good agreement with the experimental data. This means that the average strength and the coefficient of variation can be conveniently reproduced, on the assumption that the fiber strength distribution is expressed by the competing-risk model among Weibull distributions and that the scale parameter σ_{OR} is a monotonic decreasing function of annealing time. The change of the coefficient of variation cannot be explained if the single Weibull distribution is employed for the strength distribution of the fiber.

Analysis Taking a Direction of Internal Defects into Account

The analysis mentioned above has been done on the assumption that all the cracks, which mean defects inherent in the fiber, are normal to loading direction and a Weibull distribution is realized at the status of uniaxial tension. In recent years, however, it was reported [16] that the Weibull distribution should be exactly given under the equitriaxial tensile stress state if each crack existing in a material was oriented at random. Because

Figure 3. Average strength and the coefficient of variation of SiC fibers, and the predicted curves.

in this case all the cracks are situated under the same conditions of mechanics.

W. Weibull [17] discussed about the failure probability of the brittle materials at the status of multiaxial stress ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$) and suggested the unit sphere to show randomly a direction of each crack at any point of the material. Then, the cumulative distribution function is given by

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[- \int_B (K \int_A \sigma_n^m dA) dV] \quad (12)$$

σ_n is a normal stress acting on the crack plain. If a direction of the crack is expressed by angles (ϕ, θ) between the principal axes of stress and the normal line on the crack plain, this is as follows;

$$\sigma_n = \sin^2 \phi (\sigma_1 \cos^2 \theta + \sigma_2 \sin^2 \theta) + \sigma_3 \cos^2 \phi \quad (13)$$

where, $dA = \sin \phi d\phi d\theta$, A is the integrals within the material on a unit semi-sphere, and B is a volume of the material. K is a relative coefficient calculated on the assumption that eq.(12) agrees with the Weibull distribution under the uniaxial tension. As mentioned above, the concept was developed by Matsuo [16], who led the relative coefficient of the Weibull distribution realized under equitriaxial tension. Then, $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3) = (\sigma, \sigma, \sigma)$, and $\sigma_n = \sigma$, and therefore, the relative coefficient is as follows;

$$K = \frac{1}{2\pi \sigma_0^m} \quad (14)$$

Since $\sigma_n = \sigma \cos^2 \phi$ under the uniaxial tension,

$$\int_A \sigma_n^m dA = 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sigma \cdot \cos^{2m} \phi \cdot \sin \phi \cdot d\phi \cdot d\theta = \sigma^m \frac{2\pi}{2m+1}$$

In uniaxial tension, the distribution function is given by

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left\{- \frac{L}{L_0} \frac{1}{2m+1} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right\} \quad (15)$$

Additionally, he took the shear stress acting on a crack plain into account and showed the distribution function under uniaxial tension as follows;

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left\{- \frac{L}{L_0} I \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right\} \quad (16)$$

where,

$$I = \int_0^{\pi/2} \left\{ \cos^2 \phi + \frac{4}{(2-\nu)^2} \sin^2 \phi \right\}^{m/2} \cos^m \phi \cdot \sin \phi \cdot d\phi$$

In this case, σ_n is substituted by an equivalent normal stress which is defined on the basis of the strain energy release rate criterion, and concretely a penny-shaped crack is given as the crack shape. On the other

TABLE 2. Scale parameters σ_{02} modified from eqs.(15)(16).

Time min	σ_{02}	
	eq.(15)	eq.(16)
0	3.62	4.02
0.5	3.20	3.72
1	3.05	3.35

Figure 4. Relation between the nominal scale parameter " σ_{02}'' " and the scale parameter σ_{02} under uniaxial tension.

hand, all the reaction layer's cracks are situated at the same stress state under the uniaxial tension, because the cracks may be appeared at the direction normal to the loading direction as mentioned above. Therefore, eq.(3) is applied as it is. In eqs.(15) and (16), both shape parameters are samely evaluated as compared with that of eq.(3), but the scale parameter is a form to exclude an effect of the crack's direction. If the inner defects in the present work are approximately evaluated by eqs.(15) or (16), the scale parameters in Table 1. are overestimated under uniaxial tension. The scale parameters modified by eqs.(15) and (16) are shown in Table 2. The table proves that the scale parameters σ_{02} are considerably small as compared with the nominal scale parameters " σ_{02}'' " estimated by eq.(10). Figure 4 shows the analyzed curves equivalent to the nominal scale parameter calculated on the condition that the scale parameter σ_{02} is the same level for σ_{0R} . It can be understood that the inner defect is a safer crack than the reaction layer's crack because of the effect of the crack's direction. This also means that a level of the fiber strength is largely changed dependent on the cause of the fracture. Such an evaluation is very important for the interfacial problem of FRM.

CONCLUSION

For the purpose of evaluating the distribution function of the fiber strength accompanying with reaction layer between fiber and matrix metal, a competing-risk model was employed. Any of the strength distributions caused by internal defects in the fiber and by cracks formed by the premature fracture of the reaction layer were dealt as a Weibull distribution,

respectively. And it was assumed that the scale parameter estimated by the cause of the reaction layer was a monotonic decreasing function of annealing time. The results showed that the predicted values of the average strength and the coefficient of variation were in good agreement with those of the tensile test data of SiC fibers. The analysis gave another significant point that the reaction layer's crack was a dangerous defect for a fiber, on the assumption that the directions of the inner cracks were oriented at random and under equitriaxial tension the Weibull distribution was realized.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their hearty thanks to Dr.Yohtaro Matsuo, Tokyo Institute of Technology, who gave them an important comment for the present study, and to Mr.Nobuo Tabata, a graduate student of Hiroshima University (at present, Matsuda Co., Ltd.), who cooperated them in experiment.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, S.J. and Bonfield, W.J., J.Mater.Sci., 1978, 13, 1329-1334.
2. Kohara, S. and Muto, N., J.Jpn,Inst,Metals(in Japanese), 1981, 45, 411-416.
3. Ochiai, S., Osamura, K. and Murakami, Y., Z.Metallkd, 1983, 74, 44-48.
4. Ochiai, S. and Murakami, Y., ibid, 1982, 72, 827-831.
5. Fukunaga, H. and Goda, K., SAMPE Journal, 1985, 11/12, 27-31.
6. Rosen, B.W., AIAA Journal, 1964, 2, 1985-1991.
7. Batdorf, S.B., J.Rein.Plas.Comp., 1982, 1, 153-164.
8. Oh, K.P., J.Comp.Mater., 1979, 13, 311-327.
9. Mann, N.R., Schafer, R.E. and Singpurwalla, N.D., Methods for Statistical Analysis of Reliability and Life Data, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1974, pp.137-145.
10. Matsuo, Y. and Murata, H., J.Soc.Mater.Sci.,JAPAN(in Japanese), 1984, 34, 466-4471.
11. Shorshorov, M.Kh., Ustinov, L.M., Olefirenko, V.I. and Vinogradov, L.V., J.Mater.Sci., 1979, 14, 1850-1861.
12. Shiota, I. and Watanabe, O., J.Jpn,Inst,Metals(in Japanese), 1974, 38, 794-800.
13. Boggio, V. and Vingsbo, O., J.Mater.Sci., 1976, 11, 273-282.
14. Jones, J.B. and Barr, J.B. and Smith, R., ibid, 1980, 15, 2455-2465.
15. Goda, K. and Fukunaga, H., ibid, 1986, 21, 4475-4480.
16. Matsuo, Y., Bull.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 1981, 24, 495-500.
17. Weibull, W., Ingeniors Vetens Kapsakad., Handll., 1939, 151, p.1-45.